

Physiological and molecular insights into the effect of a seaweed biostimulant on enhancing fruit yield and drought tolerance in tomato

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ABSTRACT

Tomato is one of the most widely grown vegetable crops in Europe. This study describes an approach for treating tomato plants with an extract of *Ascophyllum nodosum* (ANF) prior to a stress event, which prepares the plants at the molecular level to respond more effectively to stress conditions, through a process known as molecular priming. *Solanum lycopersicum* L. cv. Micro-Tom, a dwarf tomato variety, was pre-treated with ANF via foliar spray during the flowering phase and subsequently subjected to drought conditions. ANF-treated plants exhibited enhanced growth, fruit yield, and stress tolerance under both moderate and severe drought conditions compared to untreated plants. Transcriptomic studies in leaves revealed that the priming treatment preserved the photosynthetic machinery, inducing stress-protective genes involved in ascorbate, peroxidase, GABA, glutathione, and flavanol biosynthesis. Simultaneously, the treatment repressed key senescence-related genes associated with ethylene biosynthesis, as well as several *WRKY* and *NAC* transcription factors. Metabolome analysis demonstrated that ANF induces drought tolerance by promoting the accumulation of stress-protective primary and secondary metabolites, such as GABA, proline, maltose, ascorbic acid, quercetin, and biotin, which can act as osmoprotectants and free radical scavengers during drought. Combined transcriptome and metabolome analyses suggest that ANF treatment represses the senescence process, maintains photosynthetic activity, and induces the accumulation of protective metabolites and amino acids, promoting plant survival and growth under drought. Overall, this research provides new insights into the molecular mechanisms underlying biostimulant-based molecular priming and offers a knowledge-based approach for the accurate application of this ANF molecular priming agent to increase crop productivity and mitigate yield loss during drought, contributing to food security in the era of climate change.

1. Introduction

As the global population continues to increase, demand for food

production has also risen. To meet this demand, food production must increase by an estimated 60 % by 2050 (van Dijk et al., 2021). However, the ever more prominent effects of climate change have led to more

Abbreviations: ANF, *Ascophyllum nodosum* formulation; ABA, Abscisic acid; DHA, dehydroascorbic acid; DAP, days after pollination; DEG, differentially expressed genes; GO, gene ontology; GABA, γ -aminobutyric acid; PU, primed unstressed; PS, primed stressed; ROS, reactive oxygen species; RWC, relative water content; SFC, soil field capacity; UU, unprimed unstressed.

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frequent and severe abiotic stresses such as drought, salinity, and extreme temperatures, which can significantly affect crop yields. Drought stress is a major factor limiting crop growth and yield worldwide, affecting various physiological and biochemical processes in plants, leading to reduced water uptake, impaired photosynthesis, ROS overproduction, and ultimately plant death (Fahad et al., 2017; Oguz et al., 2022). Drought alone is responsible for an average yield loss of 20 % globally, with even higher losses in some regions (Lesk et al., 2016). In crops like wheat, maize, rice, soybeans and tomato, severe drought episodes can cause yield reductions of up to 40–50 % (Gupta et al., 2020; Raja et al., 2020; Santini et al., 2022). In general, yield losses due to drought stress are more significant when stress occurs during the flowering and fruit development stages (Kondo and Morizono, 2022; Koshita and Takahara, 2004; Rering et al., 2020; Seleiman et al., 2021). Plants are more sensitive to drought stress during the flowering stage because of their increased water demand to support reproductive growth (Oguz et al., 2022; Shavrukov et al., 2017). The effect of drought stress on yield and quality depends on the severity and duration of stress, as well as on the crop species and variety (Farooq et al., 2009). Moderate drought stress at the flowering stage can result in smaller fruit size, lower yield, and reduced fruit quality, whereas severe drought stress may lead to incomplete flowering or fruit abortion (Descamps et al., 2021; Farooq et al., 2009; Morales et al., 2013; Nussbaumer et al., 2020; Turc and Tardieu, 2018). Thus, developing crops that can withstand drought while maintaining growth and productivity is essential for meeting future food demands. Therefore, innovative and sustainable approaches are urgently needed to enhance crop productivity and ensure global food security.

One such approach is the application of biostimulants, that enhance crop performance in adverse environmental conditions (Bhupenanchandra et al., 2022). These agents can induce molecular priming, where inherent plant defense systems are activated by organic or inorganic molecules, offering protection against abiotic stresses (Kerchev et al., 2020). Biostimulants comprise a wide range of compounds, including natural extracts, beneficial microorganisms, and synthetic chemicals, all of which are designed to improve plant response to stress (Ahmad et al., 2022; Castiglione et al., 2021; Zulfikar et al., 2020). Biostimulants, such as rhizobacteria, mycorrhizal fungi, humic substances, and seaweed extracts, have been investigated for their potential to induce stress tolerance, increase nutrient uptake, and mitigate the harmful effects of abiotic stressors (Ali et al., 2021; Canellas et al., 2015; Castiglione et al., 2021; Wei et al., 2022).

Among effective priming agents are extracts from the brown macroalgae *Ascophyllum nodosum* (L.). Its extracts are rich in bioactive compounds such as polysaccharides, polyphenols, vitamins, and antioxidants, which have been shown to improve plant growth, enhance stress tolerance, and increase crop yields (Deolu-Ajayi et al., 2022; Staykov et al., 2020; Sujeeth et al., 2022). The biostimulant properties of *A. nodosum* extracts have been attributed to their ability to enhance nutrient uptake, improve water use efficiency, and stimulate antioxidant defenses in plants under stress (Craigie, 2011; Khan et al., 2009). For instance, *A. nodosum* biostimulants have been reported to increase photosynthetic activity, enhance root development, and promote the synthesis of osmoprotectants, which help plants to cope with drought and salinity stresses (Kerchev et al., 2020; Verma et al., 2021; Rasul et al., 2021; Ali et al., 2022). The European Biostimulants Industry Council (EBIC, 2023) reviews the science on the mode of action of seaweed-based plant biostimulants, highlighting that they enhance drought tolerance by modulating gene expression and inducing metabolic changes, primarily through complex carbohydrates and other biomolecules, rather than plant hormones. However, despite these beneficial effects, the precise molecular mechanisms by which *A. nodosum* extracts induce stress tolerance remain poorly understood. Additionally, there is limited information on the effects of *A. nodosum* biostimulants at flowering and fruiting stage on crop plants, which is a critical factor in optimizing their application for improved stress

tolerance and crop productivity.

Therefore, this study aims to investigate the molecular mechanisms through which *Ascophyllum nodosum* biostimulants mitigate the adverse effects of drought stress on crop yield and quality. We tested a particular *Ascophyllum nodosum* formulation (ANF), a commercially available seaweed extract (SuperFifty Prime), with low viscosity and excellent solubility. *Ascophyllum nodosum* seaweed extracts are rich in the antioxidant phlorotannins and unique cell wall polysaccharides such as alginate, fucoidan and laminarin (Sharma et al., 2014). Here, we report for the first time the protective role of ANF, including details of its mechanism of action at the molecular and metabolic levels, in drought-stressed *Solanum lycopersicum* L. cv. Micro-Tom plants at the fruiting stage. We applied ANF to plants via foliar spraying at the flowering stage and subjected them to moderate and severe drought stress. The protective role of ANF against moderate and severe water-limited conditions was monitored during vegetative and fruiting stages. Our results showed that ANF application significantly improved plant growth and tolerance of tomato plants under both moderate and severe drought conditions. The treated plants had higher leaf fresh weight and improved fruit size, set, and yield compared to untreated plants under unstressed and stressed conditions. Furthermore, transcriptomic and metabolomic data analysis confirmed that ANF-treated plants maintained photosynthetic activity, and exhibited increased flavonoid levels, and primary and secondary protective metabolite accumulation (antioxidants). Moreover, combined analysis of transcriptome and metabolome data reveals that ANF provides tolerance to drought stress in tomato plants by inducing pre-accumulation of amino acids and delaying senescence at molecular level. This study highlights the protective role of ANF in tomato, especially at the fruiting stage, thereby suggesting a strategy to boost crop yields under water deficit conditions.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Plant growth conditions and rich seaweed extract application

In this study we used the dwarf Micro-Tom cultivar of tomatoes, which is widely used as a model plant for molecular and genetic studies (Martí et al., 2006). Micro-Tom seeds were sown in 1.5 lt. pots with pits and vermiculite (3:1). Plants were grown in a growth room under controlled conditions (temperature, ± 26 °C; humidity, ~ 65 %, 16 h long-day photoperiod). The plants were grown under the Mars Pro II Epistar 160 LED light, which has a Photosynthetic Photon Flux Density (PPFD) value of approximately 1015 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$ when measured at a distance of ~ 45 cm. Thus, these light sources are suitable for vegetative and reproductive growth. The spectra covered by these lights were 440, 460, 630, 660, and 730 nm.

The *Ascophyllum nodosum* formulation (ANF) used in this study is a highly concentrated extract of *A. nodosum* seaweed (SuperFifty® Prime; ≥ 495 g/L seaweed dry matter- reported by the manufacturer), was obtained from BioAtlantis Ltd., (Tralee, Ireland). *A. nodosum* extracts, are rich in unique polymers like fucoidan, laminarin, and alginates. These polymers may potentially be responsible for the priming and biostimulatory effects (Sujeeth et al., 2022), while other components of the extract may contribute synergistically (Shahzad et al., 2023). ANF is produced using an extraction process at high temperature and pressure described by (Guinan et al., 2013).

After five weeks of growth, flowers at the anthesis stage were emasculated at the full bloom stage of tomato plants (Fig. 1A). Artificial pollination was applied twice, on the day of emasculation and the day after. A total of two applications of 0.4 % v/v ANF (2 L per hectare diluted in 500 L of water) were performed on tomato plants according to the product label information provided by the manufacturer. ANF was applied as a foliar spray from the top of the plant at a ~ 15 cm distance using ~ 12 ml/plant. Special care was taken to ensure that a fine mist covered the entire leaf surface to avoid foliage overdose. The first foliar

application was performed seven days before pollination. The second foliar application was performed one day before pollination (Fig. 1A). The control plants were sprayed with water.

2.2. Drought stress treatment

The Fig. 1A shows the schematic illustration of the experimental design where drought stress was initiated at the flowering stage immediately after pollination. Watering was stopped on the day of pollination, resulting in moderate drought stress at 6 days after pollination (6 DAP) and severe drought stress at 11 days after pollination (11 DAP). To monitor the progression of recovery in drought-stressed plants, pots were re-watered 11 DAP for two days and recovery was observed on 13 DAP (Fig. 1A). We have chosen a 2-day recovery period based on studies demonstrating that many plants begin to recover physiological functions, within 1–2 days after rewatering (Chaves et al., 2009; Flexas et al., 2006). Recovery was assessed once soil field capacity reached 90–100 %, and we measured leaf fresh weight and relative water content as a key metric for recovery (Fig. 1). Soil field capacity (SFC) was measured to monitor the water status of the drought-stressed pots. The weight of the pots with soil (total solid mass) before planting was measured and then well saturated with water and left overnight. The next day, the pots with wet soil were weighed and recorded (total solid mass before drying). By the end of the drought stress the soil weight in the pots (total solid mass after drying) was measured again. The percentage of field capacity of the pots was measured using the formula: $SFC\% = ((\text{Total solid mass before drying} - \text{Total solid mass after drying}) / \text{Total solid mass}) \times 100$. The soil field capacity of control (well-watered) pots was approximately 96 %, while that of moderate drought-stressed pots was ~50 % and severe drought-stressed pots was ~25 %. Relative water content (RWC) was measured from the 6th and 7th terminal leaves of UU, US, PU, and PS samples from 6 DAP, 11 DAP, and 13 DAP plants using the method described in Yamasaki and Dillenburg (1999) to assess the water status of the plants. 6th and 7th terminal leaves were specifically chosen as they are fully developed, physiologically mature, and are neither too young nor undergoing senescence. To measure the RWC, drought-stressed leaves were harvested and weighed immediately to obtain the fresh mass (FM). The leaves were then floated in distilled water and incubated for 4-hours to obtain the turgid mass (TM). After 4 h the leaves were gently wiped with tissue paper and weighed. Then, samples were placed in a pre-heated oven at 80 °C for 24-hours to determine the dry mass (DM). The values of FM, TM and DM were used to calculate the RWC from the formula: $RWC\% = [(FM-DM)/(TM-DM)] \times 100$. To observe the effect of ANF on fruits, diameter of the fruit and number of fruits developed from artificially pollinated flowers were measured. A size range was established based on the measured diameter; fruits falling within the lower end of this range were categorized as small, those at the upper end were classified as large, and fruits with dimensions in between were designated as medium.

2.3. RNA preparation and transcriptomic analysis

The RNA samples were prepared from tomato fruits and leaves collected from well-watered plants sprayed with water (UU-Unprimed Unstressed), well-watered plants sprayed with 0.4 % ANF (PU-Primed Unstressed), drought-stressed plants sprayed with water (US-Unprimed Stressed), and drought-stressed plants treated with 0.4 % ANF (PS-Primed Stressed). The fruits and 6th and 7th terminal leaf samples from UU, PU, US, and PS tomato plants were collected at three different time points: 6, 11, and 13 days after pollination (DAP). Three biological replicates pooled from nine different plants were collected from three independent experiments.

RNA samples were sent to Novogene for library preparation (Illumina TruSeq, poly-A selection) and Illumina sequencing (150PE/40GB). Read quality was assessed using FASTQC (Andrews, 2010) and mapping was performed using Salmon (Patro et al., 2017) with selective

alignment. The average mapping rate per library was 90 % (82 % transcriptomic, 8 % decoy; Table S1). GO enrichment was performed using topGO (Alexa and Rahnenfuhrer, 2023), data analysis and visualisation were performed using VISEAGO (Brionne et al., 2019), SRPLOT (<https://www.bioinformatics.com.cn/srplot>) and R (R Core team, 2021).

To validate the transcriptomic results, qRT-PCR was conducted using the same RNA samples described above. Primers for the target genes were designed using Primer-BLAST (Ye et al., 2012), and primers are listed in Table S2. RNA samples were converted to cDNA using Thermo Scientific RevertAid RT Kit. The qRT-PCR reaction was processed using SsoFast™ EvaGreen® Supermix (Bio-Rad). Primer efficiency measurements and quantification cycles (C_q) were calculated using the qPCRsoft software. ACTIN 7 (ACT7) and EXPRESSED SEQUENCE (EXP), were used as reference genes based on literature evidence demonstrating their stable expression across various tissues and experimental conditions in tomato, making them reliable choices for normalization in qRT-PCR analysis (González-Aguilera et al., 2016; Bokhale et al., 2023). Relative mRNA expression was determined using the 2^{(-Delta C(T))} method (Kenneth and Thomas, 2001).

2.4. Metabolite profiling

The tomato fruit and leaf samples mentioned in Section 2.3 were ground to a fine powder. Each sample was aliquoted to 50 mg for gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis. Five biological replicates were used for each sample. Primary metabolites were extracted and analyzed by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) according to the procedure outlined in Lisee et al. (2006). Briefly, frozen ground material from three biological replicates was homogenized in methanol, followed by chloroform and water. The polar fraction was dried under vacuum, then derivatized with methoxyamine hydrochloride in pyridine and MSTFA. Samples were injected into a gas chromatograph coupled to a time-of-flight mass spectrometer (Pegasus HT TOF-MS). Helium was used as the carrier gas, with chromatography performed on a DB-35 column. Oven temperatures ranged from 85 °C to 360 °C. Mass spectra (m/z 70–600) were recorded at 20 scans/s and analyzed using Chroma TOF 4.5 and TagFinder 4.2 software. We used the MPI Golm Metabolome Database (<http://gmd.mpimp-golm.mpg.de>) as a reference for peak quantification and annotation (Kopka et al., 2005).

For secondary metabolite profiling, a protocol by Giavalisco et al. (2009) was used. Samples were analyzed using a Waters Acquity UPLC system with a Q-Exactive Orbitrap mass detector. A HSS T3 C18 column was operated with 0.1 % formic acid in water (Solvent A) and acetonitrile (Solvent B) as the mobile phase at 400 µL/min. Spectra were recorded in full scan mode (m/z 100–1500) with a resolution of 25,000. Data were processed using RefinerMS v. 5.3 and Xcalibur, and metabolites were identified with standard compounds, following the formats outlined by Fernie et al. (2011).

2.5. Statistical and data analysis

Differential expression analysis was performed separately on leaf and fruit data using DESeq2 (Love et al., 2014). Selected DE cut-offs were s-value < 0.001 with lfcThreshold > 1 using the apeglm shrinkage estimator (Zhu et al., 2018). This s-value cut-off is stricter than that described in the apeglm package, more closely correlating with a false discovery rate of FDR < 0.05.

Primary and secondary metabolite data presented in Fig. 5, S4, and 7, are expressed as total abundance, calculated by normalization of signal intensity to that of ribitol, which was added as an internal standard, and then by fresh weight of the material (Table S7 and S8). Total abundance of sugar and amino acid metabolite data in Fig. 6 and S6 are visualized using icon sets in Excel which shows how large is the relative abundance of a metabolite compared to the other relative abundance values in the

range. Significant differences between samples in Fig. 5, S4, S5, 6 were set at $p \leq 0.05$, as determined by ANOVA-Post hoc Tukey's test and Student's *t*-test in Fig. 7.

3. Results

3.1. The *Ascophyllum nodosum* formulation improves the phenotype and physiological response in drought stressed tomato plants

The plants were exposed to moderate (~50 % SFC, 6 DAP) and severe drought conditions (~25 % SFC, 11 DAP, Fig. 1B). The measured SFC of the well-watered control (Unprimed Unstressed, UU) and ANF control (Primed Unstressed, PU) pots was approximately 96 %, whereas the SFC of the drought-stressed pots was ~50 % (moderate drought, 6 DAP) and ~25 % (severe drought, 11 DAP), respectively (Fig. 1B).

To reveal the drought effect, relative water content (RWC) and fresh leaf weight were measured from the 6th and 7th terminal leaves of UU, US, PU, and PS samples from 6 DAP, 11 DAP, and 13 DAP plants. The graph in Fig. 1C show significant differences in RWC between the UU and PS samples at 6 DAP and 11 DAP. However, unlike at 11 DAP, no significant difference in fresh leaf weight was observed between UU and PS samples at 6 DAP. In contrast, the US plants showed a substantial decrease in both RWC and fresh leaf weight at all time points (6 DAP, 11 DAP, and 13 DAP). Additionally, while a slight reduction in RWC and fresh leaf weight was observed in severely drought-stressed PS samples, a much more pronounced decline was measured in the US plants. As a consequence, after two days of re-watering, leaf weight and RWC were not fully recovered in US plants, while PS leaves showed recovery almost equal to that of the UU and PU leaves. These results indicate that the ANF effectively protects plants under both moderate and severe drought

Fig. 1. (A) Schematic illustration of the experimental design in Micro-Tom. Foliar application of ANF was done two times, i.e., seven days before pollination (7 DBP) and one day before pollination (DBP), respectively. Control plants were sprayed with water. Six and eleven DAP plants were drought-stressed moderately (~50 % SFC) and severely (~25 % SFC). Drought-stressed plants were rewatered on 13 DAP. Control plants were watered regularly. ANF- *Ascophyllum nodosum* formulation, DBP- Days Before Pollination, DAP- Days After Pollination, SFC- Soil field capacity. (B) Measured soil field capacity, (C) relative water content and (D) fresh leaf weight in control and drought-stressed pots/plants after moderate drought (6 DAP), severe drought (11 DAP), and rewatered plants (13 DAP). Solid green and dashed green bars represent data from the Unprimed Unstressed (UU) and Primed Unstressed (PU) plants, respectively. Solid red and dashed red bars represent samples from Unprimed Stressed (US) and Primed Stressed (PS) plants, respectively. The images shown in E, F, and G were photographed at 6, 11, and 13 DAP, respectively. Leaf pictures are from the 6th and 7th terminal leaves. The scale bar in the plant and leaf pictures represents 5 cm, and in fruit, pictures represent 2 cm. The results are shown as means and standard deviations of nine pots/treatment. Different letters on each bar within the graph represent significant differences at $p \leq 0.05$ between treatments according to ANOVA-Post Hoc Tukey's test. DAP- Days After Pollination.

conditions.

The phenotypes of the plants were visually examined to determine whether ANF-induced drought tolerance occurs through growth improvement or inhibition. Pictures in Fig. 1 reveal clear phenotypic differences in plant size, the 6th and 7th terminal leaves, and fruit size between the control and drought-stressed plants. At 6 DAP (Fig. 1E), US plants were smaller than PS plants, accompanied by a reduction in leaf size due to moderate drought stress. Interestingly, UU and PS fruit sizes were nearly identical, while PU fruits were larger, and US fruits were smaller. Similar phenotypic differences were observed in the plants at 11 DAP (Fig. 1F) and 13 DAP (Fig. 1G). The plant phenotype reflects that ANF-promotes the overall plant growth, which is maintained even during drought conditions.

3.2. The *Ascophyllum nodosum* formulation improves the fruit size, fruit set and fruit yield in treated tomato plants

Next, the effects of ANF on fruit number and fruit set were identified to determine whether the priming effect of ANF improved tomato yield under control and drought conditions. The graph in Fig. 2A shows the average fruit diameter per plant in PS, PU, US, and UU. Fruits from 6 DAP, 11 DAP, and 13 DAP, US plants were significantly smaller than those from the other three variants. ANF-treated drought-stressed fruits showed no significant differences compared with the UU samples.

The graph in Fig. 2B shows the average fruit set per variant. Compared with UU, PU, and PS, the average fruit set was the lowest in the US under all three conditions. On the other hand, the fruit set in PS

Fig. 2. *Ascophyllum nodosum* formulation (ANF) improved yield in drought stressed tomato plants. (A) The diameter of fruits was measured from control, moderate drought (6 DAP), severe drought (11 DAP), and rewatered (13 DAP) plants. (B) The average fruit set per plant was monitored in the control, moderate drought (6 DAP), severe drought (11 DAP), and rewatered plants (13 DAP). (C) The percentage of fruit diameter in different classes was measured from control, moderate drought (6 DAP), severe drought (11 DAP), and rewatered (13 DAP) plants. The fruit size were classified into three categories: large, medium, and small. In 6 DAP samples, small, medium, and large fruits measured 2–4 mm, 4–6 mm, and 6–9 mm, respectively. For 11 DAP samples, sizes were 3–8 mm (small), 8–12 mm (medium), and 12–16 mm (large). In 13 DAP samples, small, medium, and large fruits measured 9–13 mm, 13–17 mm, and 17–20 mm, respectively. The red, green, and orange bars represent large, medium, and small fruit sizes, respectively. (D) The total number of fruits was counted from Unprimed Unstressed (UU), Primed Unstressed (PU), Unprimed Stressed (US) and Primed Stressed (PS) plants. The green, orange, and red bars represent the numbers of unripe, semi-ripe, and ripe fruits, respectively. (E) The weight of total fruits per plant at first harvest was weighed in UU, PU, US and PS plants. The results are presented as means and standard deviations of fruits from the nine pots. Different letters on each bar within the graph represent significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) between treatments, according to ANOVA-Post Hoc Tukey's test. Asterisk (*) denote a significant differences in mean fruit set between treatments ($p \leq 0.05$) at each timepoint, as determined by ANOVA-Post Hoc Tukey's test. Solid green and dashed green bars represent data from the Unprimed Unstressed (UU) and Primed Unstressed (PU) plants, respectively. Solid red and dashed red bars represent samples from Unprimed Stressed (US) and Primed Stressed (PS) plants, respectively.

Fig. 3. Comparison of differentially expressed genes in Micro-Tom leaf and fruit samples. The number of up- and down-regulated genes in PU/UU, PS/UU and US/ UU pairwise comparison at 6 DAP, 11 DAP and 13 DAP leaf (A) and fruit samples (B). Solid green and dashed green bars represent up- and down-regulated genes in the leaves, respectively. Solid red and dashed red bars represent up- and down-regulated genes in fruits, respectively. Venn diagram showing the overlapping DEGs between PU/UU, PS/UU, and US/UU at 6, 11, and 13 DAP in leaf (C) and fruit samples (D). Venn diagram of (E) upregulated and downregulated genes in US/PS in moderate and severe drought leaves and fruits. Up and down arrows indicate opposite expression patterns. UU- Unprimed Unstressed, PU- Primed Unstressed, US- Unprimed Stressed, PS- Primed Stressed.

plants was not significantly different from that in UU plants, and a peak in the fruit set was observed after two days of re-watering. PU plants displayed higher fruit set (~95 %) than UU plants.

The graph in Fig. 2C shows the distribution of fruits into three classes: large, medium, and small in 6 DAP, 11 DAP, and 13 DAP plants. The graph shows that PU plants produced the highest percentage (~80 %) of large fruits. The PS plants had ~65 % medium, ~15 % small, and ~20 % large fruits under moderate stress, whereas in severely stressed and rewatered plants, ~95 % of the fruits were medium-sized. On the contrary, US plants produced more (~60 %) small-sized tomatoes.

The total number of fruits was counted during the final harvest. Fruits were distributed into three ripeness stages based on color: green as unripe, orange as semi-ripe, and red as ripe. Fig. 2D shows that PU and PS plants had fewer unripe fruits and more semi-ripe and ripe fruits than UU and US plants. Moreover, PU plants produced the highest number of ripe fruits, whereas US plants yielded the lowest number (Fig. 2D). The graph in Fig. 2E shows the weight of tomato fruits per plant during the first harvest. Compared to UU, higher fruit yield was observed in PU, while PS had a yield similar to UU (Fig. 2E).

Together the results confirmed that ANF improves fruit size, set, and yield in tomato plants grown under both normal and drought-stressed conditions.

3.3. Global transcriptome dynamics in tomato leaves and fruits

To reveal the drought stress-adaptive molecular changes induced by ANF under stressed and unstressed conditions, comparative transcriptome analysis using RNA sequencing was performed (Table S3). There was a measurable priming-specific response in leaves several days after spraying (PU/UU), and the number of differentially expressed genes (DEGs) progressively increased under both stress conditions in the leaves and fruits (Fig. 3A and B). The number of DEGs in fruits was far

less pronounced at 6 DAP, although more DEGs were observed at 11 and 13 DAP than in the corresponding leaf samples (Fig. 3B). The number of dysregulated genes was consistently higher in the US samples than in the PS samples in both tissues, and was reduced in the 13 DAP rewatered samples. The more substantial reduction in the number of dysregulated genes in the rewatered PS samples (13 DAP) highlights the enhanced recovery efficiency of ANF-primed plants compared to unprimed plants. The Venn diagrams in Fig. 3C and D show the overlapping genes in tomato leaves and fruits between PU/UU, PS/UU, and US/UU under all three conditions (6 DAP, 11 DAP, and 13 DAP). To verify the robustness of the transcriptomic data, we analyzed the expression of individual genes using qRT-PCR in independent biological replicates (Figure S1). The expression patterns of the selected genes were similar to those identified by RNA sequencing. Overall, the results showed that under drought stress both leaves and fruits had substantially fewer DEGs when pre-treated with ANF than unprimed samples.

3.4. Molecular changes induced by the *Ascophyllum nodosum* formulation under normal and drought-stressed conditions

To understand the mechanisms by which the *Ascophyllum nodosum* formulation (ANF) promotes plant growth, we investigated the gene expression profiles in ANF-treated plants under both normal and drought-stressed conditions. Under normal conditions, we identified 28 upregulated and 15 downregulated genes in all ANF-treated (PU) leaves, alongside three consistently upregulated genes in fruits across all sampling dates (6, 11, and 13 DAP; Table S4). Notably, in ANF-treated leaves, genes associated with sterol biosynthesis were upregulated, while those involved in biotic and abiotic stress responses, as well as senescence processes, were downregulated across the 6, 11, and 13 DAP samples. In fruits, ANF treatment resulted in the upregulation of genes linked to fruit development, maturation, and ripening.

Under drought conditions, the transcriptional responses varied significantly between US and PS leaf and fruit samples at 6 and 11 DAP (Fig. 3E). US leaves showed significant gene expression shifts under moderate drought, while PS leaves exhibited fewer transcriptional changes, indicating moderated stress response due to priming (Fig. 3E). This pattern persisted under severely drought-stressed leaves (11 DAP), where a similar but less pronounced difference was observed. In fruits, US samples had the most DEGs under both conditions. Interestingly, there was substantial overlap in gene expression between US and PS fruits at 11 DAP but not in the 6 DAP samples. Of note, shared genes found in US and PS were enriched for gene ontology terms related to the basic stress response (Table S5), suggesting that they are not modulated by the ANF treatment; thus, we did not analyze them further.

Next, we investigated the gene ontology (GO) enrichment of the US- and PS-specific DEGs in leaf and fruit samples (Table S5). The bubble plot in Fig. 4A includes key stress-related enriched GO terms such as hormones, photosynthesis, and stress response, while detailed GO term enrichment is shown in Figure S2 and S3. In US leaves, genes related to photosynthesis were downregulated (Fig. 4A), while in moderately-drought stressed PS leaves enrichment of GO terms are linked to metabolic processes such as threonine, sterol and glucan metabolism

(Fig. 4A). Additionally, PS leaves under severe drought conditions exhibited upregulation of genes associated with flavonol biosynthesis and negative regulation of senescence. The US samples during moderate drought showed enrichment for stress hormone-related GO terms, whereas PS samples under severe drought exhibited links to hormones associated with stress tolerance (Fig. 4A). In US fruits, samples exhibited GO term enrichment in stress response-related genes, with notable downregulation of genes involved in lactone biosynthesis, which are crucial for fruit aroma and flavor (Figure S3). In turn, ANF-treated fruits under severe drought conditions showed no distinct upregulation enrichment, with downregulated genes mainly enriched in the stress response, secondary cell wall biogenesis, and negative regulation of endopeptidase activity (Figure S3). Thus, specific insights into ANF-induced stress-adaptive mechanisms at the molecular level in PS fruits have not been identified by the GO enrichment analysis.

We further analyzed the stress-related DEGs uniquely modulated only in the PS leaves (252 for moderate drought and 371 for severe drought), to explore molecular protection pathways specific to drought stress tolerance induced by ANF at the vegetative stage. The graph in Fig. 4B shows the number of upregulated and downregulated genes linked to stress response in PS leaves at 6 and 11 DAP (Table S6). In

Fig. 4. Gene ontology enrichment of differentially expressed genes in Micro-Tom leaf samples. Selected GO enrichment of upregulated and downregulated genes in Unprimed Stressed (US) moderate drought leaves, US severe drought leaves, and Primed Stressed (PS) severe drought leaves. Red bubble plot represents GO enrichment of upregulated genes and green bubble plot represents GO enrichment of downregulated genes. The size of the bubble represents the percentage of gene frequency, and the color bar represents the p-value. The full list of GO-enriched categories is given in Supplementary Figure S2 and S3. (B) Stress-related differentially expressed down- and up-regulated genes in PS- moderate and severe drought stressed leaves. Red bars represent upregulated genes, and green bars represent downregulated genes.

moderately drought-stressed PS leaves, we observed upregulation of 10 genes associated with abiotic stress responses, including *WRKY46* and *NAC6* transcription factors, three genes involved in biotic stress responses, and three other genes implicated in stress tolerance (Fig. 4B). The upregulated stress-tolerance genes encode β -amylase, L-ascorbate oxidase, and peroxidases. In contrast, severely drought-stressed leaves exhibited upregulation of 17 genes associated with abiotic stress, including *WRKY* and *bHLH* transcription factors, and seven genes associated with stress tolerance that function in γ -aminobutyric acid (GABA), glutathione, and flavanol biosynthesis (Table S6). Taken together, the differential expression of stress-responsive genes in primed leaves suggests that ANF application enhances stress tolerance mechanisms as stress intensifies.

3.5. Changes in the abundance of protective metabolites induced by the *Ascophyllum nodosum* formulation

The transcriptomic data indicated that ANF induces stress-adaptive responses in tomato plants. We expected that increased stress protection in primed plants would be accompanied by the accumulation of stress-preventive metabolites such as antioxidants. Of the 60 profiled primary metabolites, 14 protective metabolites showed varying levels in UU, PU, US, and PS leaves (Fig. 5A; Table S7). The osmoprotectants alanine, proline, fructose, glucose, raffinose, glutamate, mannitol, maltose, and the antioxidant-related metabolites ascorbic acid, dehydroascorbic acid (DHA), dehydroascorbic acid dimer (DDHA), GABA, and putrescine were more abundant in PU than in UU in all leaf samples. Compared with US, PS leaves had higher levels of alanine, DHA, DDHA, and glutamate under moderate drought but remained unchanged under severe drought samples. Interestingly, a prominent increase in maltose was observed in both the PU and PS samples under all conditions. In fruit samples, except for a few metabolites ANF did not induce major differences in the levels of primary protective metabolites (Figure S4).

Of the 183 profiled secondary metabolites, seven out of eleven protective metabolites in leaf samples (Figure 5B; Table S8), namely, caffeic acid, quercetin, abscisic acid (ABA), biotin, homogentisic acid, rutin, and quinic acid, showed increased abundance in PU compared to UU under all three conditions. Compared to US, the accumulation of quercetin, ABA, biotin, dehydrotomatine, lycoperside, and rutin was higher in 6 DAP but remained unchanged in 11 DAP, PS leaf samples. Similar to primary metabolites, secondary metabolites in fruits showed no major differences between primed, stressed, and control samples (Figure S4).

3.6. Sugars and amino acid accumulation induced by the *Ascophyllum nodosum* formulation

Next, we monitored the concentration of amino acid metabolites and the overall distribution of sugars. As shown in Fig. 6A, the highest

Fig. 5. Stress protective metabolites in tomato leaves. Graphs of protective primary metabolites (A) and protective secondary metabolites (B) in tomato leaf samples at 6, 11, and 13 DAP. Solid green and dashed green bars represent samples from Unprimed Unstressed (UU), and Primed Unstressed (PU) leaves. The solid yellow and dashed yellow bars represent samples from Primed Stressed (PS) and Unprimed Stressed (US) leaves, respectively. Data are expressed as total abundance, calculated by normalization of signal intensity to that of ribitol, which was added as an internal standard, and then by fresh weight of the material. Different letters on each bar represent significant differences at $p < 0.05$ according to ANOVA-Post Hoc Tukey's test; GABA, γ -aminobutyric acid, DHA, dehydroascorbic acid, DDHA, dehydroascorbic acid dimer.

Fig. 6. Amino acid metabolites in tomato leaf and fruit samples. Icon sets of amino acid metabolites from Unprimed Unstressed (UU), Primed Unstressed (PU), Primed Stressed (PS) and Unprimed Stressed (US) tomato leaves (A) and fruit (B) samples at 6, 11 and 13 DAP. Data are expressed as the total abundance in the form of icon sets from maximum to minimum, which are distinguished by a threshold value. Different letters represent significant differences at $p \leq 0.05$, according to ANOVA-Post hoc Tukey's test; GABA, γ -aminobutyric acid.

number of amino acids accumulated significantly in response to moderate (6 DAP) and severe drought (11 DAP) stress in US leaves. Interestingly, amino acid metabolites were more abundant in PU and PS fruit samples compared to those in UU and US, respectively, under all three conditions (Fig. 6B). Similarly, six out of ten and four out of six significant sugar metabolites were more abundant in US leaf samples at 6 DAP and 11 DAP, respectively, compared to PS samples (Figure S5). However, unlike the leaves, very few sugars differed significantly among the fruit samples.

3.7. Impact of the *Ascophyllum nodosum* formulation on amino acid levels and senescence-related genes under drought stress

Next, we compared the abundance of amino acid metabolites only between PU and US leaves (Fig. 7) and examined the genes linked to senescence in these samples at 6 and 11 DAP. This was done to confirm that the increase in the levels of amino acids in US is linked to the

activation of senescence, while in PU it may be attributed to the priming effect of ANF, which induces plant growth and stress tolerance.

In Fig. 7, PU 6 DAP leaves exhibited an increase in six amino acids, including serine, alanine, GABA, glutamate and proline, whereas in 11 DAP, PU leaves only two amino acids i.e. serine and alanine showed increased abundance. In US 6 DAP leaves, ten amino acids were highly abundant while US 11 DAP leaves had elevated levels of 14 amino acids. In PU leaves, the accumulation of GABA, glutamate, alanine, serine, and proline suggests that ANF treatment enhances stress protection and metabolism, as these metabolites are known to play key roles in osmo-protection and redox balance (Ingrisano et al., 2023; Hasan et al., 2021; Qiu et al., 2020; Kishor et al., 2020; Hayat et al., 2012). In US plants, the higher amino acid levels at both time points indicate a metabolic response to drought-induced senescence, likely involving protein degradation. This observation was further supported by the analysis of senescence-related genes, where 20 and 13 positive regulators of senescence were upregulated in US leaves at 6 DAP and 11 DAP,

	6 DAP		11 DAP	
	PU	US	PU	US
Serine	121.8	61.0	102.7	61.0
Threonine	25.3	22.6	24.4	22.6
Alanine	353.0	75.5	234.5	75.5
GABA	22.4	8.9	8.9	14.4
Glutamate	212.7	137.1	187.3	242.2
Proline	828.4	293.2	405.5	505.8
Lysine	3.5	10.3	3.4	10.3
Putrescine	25.1	50.5	21.5	50.5
β -Alanine	0.9	1.3	0.7	0.9
Asparagine	1.0	9.4	1.2	9.4
Glutamine	19.0	39.0	12.8	39.0
Isolucine	7.2	44.0	11.2	44.0
Leucine	7.2	33.1	11.8	33.1
Tryptophan	2.7	62.3	9.0	62.3
Methionine	0.8	2.1	1.0	2.1
Phenylalanine	7.2	10.9	6.9	10.9
Valine	17.0	79.2	22.2	79.2
Pyroglutamic acid	225.6	234.8	321.4	234.8

Fig. 7. Amino acid metabolic differences between PU and US leaf samples. Yellow and green boxes represent significantly lower and higher amino acid metabolite levels, respectively, between PU and US leaf samples at 6 and 11 DAP, respectively. The amino acids in the white boxes are not significantly different. Data are expressed as total abundance, calculated by normalization of signal intensity to that of ribitol, which was added as an internal standard, and then by fresh weight of the material. Significant differences between PU and US samples were set at $p \leq 0.05$, as determined by the Student's *t*-test.

respectively (Table 1). In contrast, only three genes - *WRKY3*, *WRKY70*, and Protein Phosphatase 2C (*PP2C*) that are known for their roles in the negative regulation of senescence, were slightly upregulated in PU leaves (Durian et al., 2020; Hichri et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2023; Ülker et al., 2007). Thus, while amino acids accumulate in both PU and US, ANF-treated plants regulate this accumulation for enhanced growth and stress tolerance, whereas untreated plants show accumulation as a result of stress-triggered senescence at the cellular level.

4. Discussion

4.1. The *Ascophyllum nodosum* formulation improves the yield of tomato under both non-stressed and drought-stressed conditions

The rapidly changing global climate poses challenges to agricultural productivity, with drought being a major threat to crop yield and food security (Seleiman et al., 2021; Zia et al., 2021). Therefore, we evaluated the efficiency of ANF in improving plant tolerance to moderate and severe drought. As demonstrated above, no significant variation was found in leaf RWC or fresh leaf weight between UU and moderately drought-stressed PS samples (Fig. 1), while US leaves exhibited a pronounced decline in these metrics. Re-watering resulted in robust recovery of PS leaves, emphasizing the protective role of ANF. Higher RWC and fresh leaf weight in ANF-treated plants under drought stress reflect better water retention, which is crucial for maintaining cell turgor and physiological activities, such as photosynthesis and nutrient transport, under limited water availability (Seleiman et al., 2021; Qiao et al., 2024). Additionally, maintained RWC is directly linked to delayed onset of drought-induced senescence (Farooq et al., 2009; Semwal and Khanna-Chopra, 2018). This indicates that ANF improves overall plant health and productivity by maintaining water retention and physiological activities in drought condition.

Table 1

List of senescence-related genes differentially expressed in US and PU leaf samples at 6 and 11 DAP. The values represent \log_2 fold change.

Senescence-related genes in leaves		6 DAP		11 DAP	
Gene ID	Gene Name	PU vs. UU	US vs. UU	PU vs. UU	US vs. UU
Solyc01g095080	1-Aminocyclopropane-1-carboxylic acid synthase 2 (ACS2)		5.0	-2.2	
Solyc02g067660	Senescence associated carboxylesterase 101		1.7		
Solyc03g007380	WRKY52		2.2		
Solyc04g005050	Peptidase metalloproteinase protein		3.2		
Solyc04g009440	NAC domain protein AY498713		2.5		
Solyc06g009140	Late embryogenesis abundant protein (LEA5)		3.1		
Solyc07g045030	NAC domain transcription factor		2.3		
Solyc07g049530	1-Aminocyclopropane-1-carboxylate oxidase 1 (ACO1)		3.2		
Solyc08g008280	WRKY53		2.4		
Solyc02g071130	WRKY71		2.2		2.7
Solyc02g076910	Cysteine protease		9.8		9.9
Solyc10g081980	Late embryogenesis abundant protein (LEA2)		3.8		2.1
Solyc09g092500	UDP Glycosyltransferase 75C1 (UGT75C1)		1.6		1.5
Solyc04g005610	NAC domain-containing protein 2 (NAP2)		2.6		3.2
Solyc05g007770	NAC1		2.6		1.4
Solyc06g060230	Nam like protein 1 (SINAMI)		1.2		1.3
Solyc07g051890	MAP kinase kinase kinase 53 (MPKKK53)		2.8		3.0
Solyc08g065610	Vacuolar processing enzyme-1b		2.9		1.6
Solyc09g025310	NAC domain containing protein				3.5
Solyc02g088180	NAC2				2.9
Solyc04g005250	SAM-dependent Mtase DRM protein				2.4
Solyc06g076400	Protein phosphatase			1.2	1.8
Solyc03g095770	WRKY70	1.2	2.0		
Solyc09g015770	WRKY3	1.1	2.1		

Growth retardation and conserving resources for survival is an evolutionary trait that allows plants to combat stress (Kanojia and Dijkwel, 2018; Zhang et al., 2020). Previous studies have demonstrated that biostimulants such as seaweed extracts, promote physiological resilience in plants by enhancing water uptake and reducing oxidative stress (Carmody et al., 2020; Jacomassi et al., 2022; Rosário Rosa et al., 2021). Similar to our findings, ANF-treated plants exhibited enhanced reproductive (fruiting) stage performance. Notably, ANF-treated plants predominantly produced medium-to large-sized fruits, whereas untreated plants under drought stress yielded a higher percentage of small fruits (Fig. 2C). Furthermore, at the ripening stage, ANF-treated plants, especially PS, showed an increase in ripe fruits, indicating a potential acceleration in fruit maturation even under stress (Fig. 2D). This indicates that improved water retention not only contributes to growth but also increased fruit size, set, and overall yield, even under stressed conditions (Fig. 2). Overall, our results clearly demonstrated that ANF significantly improved fruit-set and yield in tomato plants, both under non-stressed and drought stress conditions.

4.2. The *Ascophyllum nodosum* formulation promoted growth-related gene networks at vegetative and fruiting stage in tomato

Better plant growth is crucial because it serves as a fundamental determinant of overall health and productivity (Hilty et al., 2021). In this context, ANF shows promising potential, particularly for improving the growth of tomato plants. An in-depth analysis of the transcripts in PU leaves highlighted the increased expression of several genes related to growth and developmental processes at 6, 11, and 13 DAP. The transcriptomic data revealed increased levels of mRNAs encoding for proteins, such as phosphoenolpyruvate/phosphate translocator, members of the shikimate pathway and flavonoid biosynthesis and F-box family proteins, which are essential for both developmental and environmental signals in plants (Knappe et al., 2003; Zhang et al., 2017). Our analysis also identified an increase in the transcripts of the *R2R3-MYB* transcription factor 13 and *bZIP* transcription factor *TAG6*, which regulate plant growth and development (Huang et al., 2018; Stotz et al., 2013). In this study, we noticed that a gene encoding a protein called NRT1/ PTR FAMILY, which is specifically involved in the regulation of nitrate uptake and transport in plants (Chiba et al., 2015), was significantly upregulated at all sampling dates in PU leaves (6, 11, and 13 DAP). The marked upregulation of growth-related genes highlights the pivotal role of ANF in improving plant growth, making ANF an intriguing focus for further study of its growth-promoting potential.

Growth-related genes in leaves: Plants use sterols, such as campesterol and sitosterol, to stabilize their membranes and regulate permeability, which are crucial for optimal growth and development (Dufourc, 2008). Our analysis showed that ANF-treated leaves under non-stressed conditions consistently elevated the expression of genes associated with sterol biosynthesis at every sampling date (6, 11, and 13 DAP; Table S4). Important genes, involved in the biosynthesis of sterols, steroidal alkaloids, and maintenance of sterol composition, such as *GAME9*, *METHYLSTEROL MONOOXYGENASE 1-2*, and *METHYLSTEROL MONOOXYGENASE 2-1*, were upregulated in PU leaves (Cárdenas et al., 2016; Catterou et al., 2001; Choe et al., 1999; Luccioni et al., 2002; Rasbery et al., 2007; Song et al., 2019). Moreover, we found upregulation of multiple glycosyltransferase genes involved in the biosynthesis of sterol glycosides, which can enhance cell membrane integrity (Kobayashi et al., 2001; Ramirez-Estrada et al., 2017). Our results further showed increased expression of cytochrome P450 enzymes in PU leaves, which are crucial for the biosynthesis of fatty acids, sterols, and cell wall components (Minerdi et al., 2023). Notably, the obtained data also highlight that in moderate drought, upregulated genes in PS leaves were also enriched in sterol biosynthesis. In summary, our findings indicate that induced expression of sterol metabolism-related genes in both unstressed (PU) and drought-stressed (PS) leaves is one of the mechanisms through which ANF priming exerts its positive effects.

Growth-related genes in fruits: Our data showed that tomato plants treated with ANF produced larger marketable tomatoes (Fig. 2). Upon further analysis of the transcriptomic data, only three genes in the PU fruits were differentially expressed by ANF at all sampling dates (6, 11, and 13 DAP; Table S3). Notably, the ABC transporter G family member 11 gene, linked to fruit development, was upregulated in ANF-treated samples, correlating with larger fruit sizes (Ofori et al., 2018; Fig. 2). Additionally, genes from the tetratricopeptide repeat (TPR)-like superfamily, regulating pericarp cell size and fruit size, were also upregulated (Zhou et al., 2021). The downregulation of a gene encoding a pistil-specific extensin-like protein suggests ANF may enhance pollen tube development and fruit set (Alves et al., 2019; Eberle et al., 2013). The process of carbohydrate partitioning from source to sink is essential for tomato fruit development, determining both the quantity and quality of fruit production (Nguyen-Quoc and Foyer, 2001; Osorio et al., 2014). Interestingly, our study found increased sucrose accumulation at the metabolite level in leaves and fruits treated with ANF, contributing to the larger fruit size and better quality at harvest (Figure S5). In summary, ANF treatment significantly improved tomato fruit size and yield under both stressed and non-stressed conditions, demonstrating potential economic benefits for farmers through enhanced fertilization and marketable fruit quality.

4.3. The *Ascophyllum nodosum* formulation enhanced drought tolerance by inducing molecular protection pathways in tomato

Stress protective gene network: Plants have evolved various methods for handling environmental stress. One key strategy is the production of antioxidants such as flavonoids that counteract strong oxidizers like ROS (Jan et al., 2021; Salam et al., 2023; Shomali et al., 2022). While ROS can be detrimental when overproduced under stress, plants have a built-in mechanism to neutralize these harmful molecules (Gill et al., 2012; Kaushik and Roychoudhury, 2014). Our transcriptomic data reveal significant differences in gene expression between US and PS leaves, particularly highlighting the upregulation of stress-tolerant genes in PS plants (Fig. 4B). For example, genes involved in flavonoid biosynthesis, such as *chalcone synthase (CHS2)* and the MYB TF *SITHM27*, were notably upregulated in PS leaves. Flavonoids play an essential role in mitigating oxidative damage by scavenging ROS, and the increased expression of these genes suggests an enhanced capacity for ROS detoxification (Adato et al., 2009; Al-Attala et al., 2014; España et al., 2014; Heredia et al., 2015; Schijlen et al., 2007; Wang et al., 2020a). In addition, our data show ANF treatment increased the expression of genes directly involved in ROS detoxification, such as Glutathione S-transferase and L-ascorbate oxidase in PS leaf samples. Glutathione and ascorbate are key components of the plant antioxidant defense system, helping to reduce ROS levels and protect cellular structures from oxidative damage (Gill et al., 2012; Yan et al., 2021; Csiszár et al., 2014; Molina et al., 2021). The physiological results from ANF treated plants also provide evidence of enhanced drought tolerance in plants. GABA plays a key role in plant stress tolerance by improving photosynthesis, scavenging ROS, and activating antioxidant enzymes (Al-Quraan et al., 2015; Bouché and Fromm, 2004; Yong et al., 2017). The increase in GABA biosynthesis-related gene, as evidenced by the upregulation of glutamate decarboxylase 3 (*GAD3*), further confirms the role of ANF in enhancing plant stress tolerance (Akihiro et al., 2008; Takayama et al., 2015). Moreover, in moderately drought-stressed PS leaves, GO terms linked to sterol biosynthesis and threonine and lignin catabolism were enriched (Fig. 4A). Threonine, a precursor for isoleucine biosynthesis, plays a crucial role in osmotic stress response and abiotic stress tolerance (Joshi et al., 2010; Muthuramalingam et al., 2018; Hildebrandt et al., 2015). Additionally, lignin deposition in the cell wall, is also known to enhance drought tolerance in plants by strengthening cell walls and reducing water loss (Choi et al., 2023). The enrichment of sterol biosynthesis, along with threonine and lignin catabolism, indicates that ANF primed plants under moderate drought

stress are maintaining normal growth and adapting efficiently to the stress conditions. These transcriptomic findings reveal that ANF induces the expression of a network of genes critical for stress adaptation. This enhanced genetic response likely contributes to the phenotypic improvements observed in ANF treated drought stressed plants, highlighting the molecular mechanisms by which plants adapt to environmental stress.

Hormones play a pivotal role in plant stress responses. ABA, is the well-known stress hormone that regulates stomatal closure during drought, reduces water loss and enables plants to conserve water (Ibrahim and Jaafar, 2013; Kanojia et al., 2021; Sah et al., 2016; Waterland et al., 2010). On the other hand, salicylic acid (SA) is another stress hormone that plays a complex role in plant responses to drought stress, acting primarily as a signaling molecule rather than providing direct tolerance (Borsani et al., 2001; Miura and Tada, 2014). The upregulation of SA triggers the activation of downstream genes involved in stress responses, including the production of ROS, which signals the plant that it is under stress (Borsani et al., 2001; Miura and Tada, 2014). In this study, both ABA and SA were found to be more abundant in US 6 DAP leaves, indicating that unprimed plants show reduction in growth because of greater stress (Fig. 4A). This suggests that while ABA and SA are crucial in signaling stress, they do not necessarily confer increased tolerance. Conversely, PS severe drought leaves did not show elevated levels of these stress hormones; instead, GO terms related to stress-tolerance hormones like cytokinins, brassinosteroids, and jasmonic acid were enriched in upregulated genes (Fig. 4A). Many studies have demonstrated the role of these hormones in the enhancement of plant stress tolerance (Chaudhuri et al., 2022; Kim et al., 2021; Raza et al., 2021; Avni et al., 2020; Gujjar & Supaibulwatana, 2019). For instance, cytokinin plays a crucial role in plant adaptation to osmotic stress by reducing ROS levels, enhancing plant growth, and delaying senescence (Avni et al., 2020; Gujjar & Supaibulwatana, 2019). In our study, ANF treatment induced these positive effects, with cytokinin-mediated pathways significantly enriched in PS severe drought leaves (Fig. 4A), leading to improved growth and stress resilience. Similarly, brassinosteroids, which are essential for modulating plant responses to various environmental stresses through signaling interactions with transcription factors, showed enrichment in PS leaves, further contributing to their stress tolerance (Ahmed et al., 2020; Chaudhuri et al., 2022). Jasmonic acid, known for its role in both biotic and abiotic stress tolerance, also exhibited increased levels under severe drought ANF treated leaves, highlighting its contribution to strengthening plant defenses and improving overall drought resistance (Kim et al., 2021; Raza et al., 2021). These findings suggest that, while hormonal upregulation in US plants indicates higher stress sensitivity, PS plants rely on a more balanced and stress-tolerant hormonal response, involving hormones known to enhance resilience. This differential hormonal regulation highlights the importance of ANF priming in improving plant tolerance to drought stress.

Stress-protective metabolite network: Plant metabolites play a pivotal role in the overall adaptation to environmental stresses, allowing plants to mitigate the adverse impacts of external stressors like drought (Irchhaiya et al., 2015; Lamalakshmi Devi et al., 2017; Singh et al., 2015). Our metabolomic profiling revealed that protective metabolites play a key role in enhancing tomato plant tolerance to drought, particularly in plants primed with ANF (Fig. 5). In primed leaves, ANF induced the accumulation of mannitol that acts as a hydroxyl radical scavenger and reduces lipid peroxidation during drought stress (Kaya et al., 2013; Stoop et al., 1996). Proline, a well-known osmoprotectant, was also found at higher levels in primed leaf samples. It plays a key role in drought tolerance by stabilizing proteins and scavenging free radicals (Freitas et al., 2019; Hayat et al., 2012; Liang et al., 2013). Additionally, ANF increased the accumulation of ascorbic acid, DHA and DDHA in leaves. These are essential components of the ascorbate-glutathione cycle, a major antioxidant system that detoxifies ROS and preserves cellular integrity under stress (Akram et al., 2017; Hasanuzzaman et al.,

2019; Smirnoff and Wheeler, 2000). The abundance of GABA was also significantly higher in primed leaves, reflecting ANF role in enhancing antioxidant enzyme activity in plant stress tolerance (Hasan et al., 2021; Zhou et al., 2021). Like transcriptomic data, primary metabolomic data also presents a consistent depiction where the upregulation of genes linked to the biosynthesis of GABA, proline, ascorbate, and glutathione directly corresponds to the elevated accumulation of these metabolites.

Secondary metabolite analysis further showed higher levels of antioxidant compounds like caffeic acid and quercetin in primed leaves. Caffeic acid strengthens cell walls, while quercetin exhibits strong antioxidant properties, contributing to enhanced stress tolerance in ANF treated plants (Mehmood et al., 2021; Riaz et al., 2018; Arikan et al., 2023; Jańczak-Pieniżek et al., 2021; Singh et al., 2021). Other secondary metabolites including biotin, rutin, quinic acid, and homogentisic acid, also increased in response to ANF treatment, all of which are recognized for their ROS scavenging abilities and roles in improving plant tolerance to abiotic stresses (Collakova and DellaPenna, 2003; Mattos and Moretti, 2016; Ahmed et al., 2020; Singh et al., 2017, 2021; Wang et al., 2020b). Collectively, these findings show that the accumulation of stress-protective metabolites in ANF-treated tomato plants enhances drought tolerance and promotes better growth. However, the abundance of such metabolites was not as pronounced in fruits, suggesting that ANF primarily targets the vegetative phase to counteract the potential harm of drought, thereby indirectly benefiting fruit growth and productivity.

4.4. Combined analysis of transcriptome and metabolome reveals the key molecular mechanism induced by *Ascophyllum nodosum* formulation

Plants experience stress-induced senescence, an irreversible phase in leaf development that accelerates in response to environmental factors such as drought (Kanojia et al., 2020). Senescence is marked by the degradation of proteins, leading to amino acid accumulation in leaves, which are then transported to other growing tissues (Almutairi et al., 2022; Hajjibarat and Saidi, 2022; Soudry et al., 2005). In turn, in young leaves, amino acids play a crucial role in promoting growth and improve tolerance to various abiotic stressors (Almutairi et al., 2022; Garcia et al., 2011; Mohammadi and Khoshgoftarmanesh, 2014; Mohammadipour and Souiri, 2019).

Our combined transcriptomic and metabolomic analyses suggest that ANF induces a molecular mechanism that delays the onset of senescence and enhances drought tolerance in tomato plants. This is supported by the downregulation of key senescence-related genes, observed consistently across all time points in PU leaves (6 DAP, 11 DAP, and 13 DAP). For instance, the putative invertase inhibitor gene, which regulates senescence by blocking ABA-induced leaf aging, was significantly downregulated in PU leaves (Jin et al., 2009). RNA interference transgenic tomato lines expressing this gene have been shown to prolong the lifespan of leaves by blocking ABA-induced senescence (Jin et al., 2009). Likewise, the downregulation of ABSCISIC ACID STRESS RIPENING 5 (ASR5), a gene involved in stress-induced senescence, further supports the delayed senescence in ANF-primed plants (Golan et al., 2014). Similar findings were reported in *Petunia* where orthologous genes were linked to early senescence initiation (Chang et al., 2003). Additionally, PS severe drought leaf samples displayed GO enrichment for negative regulation of senescence (Fig. 4A), confirming the role of ANF in delaying senescence at molecular level in both unstressed and stressed conditions.

Interestingly, while transcriptomic data in PS leaves indicated enrichment of GO terms associated with the negative regulation of senescence-related genes, metabolomic data showed an accumulation of amino acids, typically associated with senescence progression, in both PU and US samples (Fig. 6). This observation left some ambiguity regarding the exact mechanisms involved. However, this was clarified when we further compared amino acid metabolite levels and senescence-related gene transcripts between US and PU leaf samples

(Fig. 7, Table 1). The results confirmed that amino acid accumulation is the outcome of senescence progression only in US, because the abundance of amino acids in US was higher than that in PU samples and this was accompanied by the upregulation of senescence-related genes exclusively in US leaves.

Previous studies have highlighted the dual role of amino acids in active growth and senescence. For example, young leaves in peach and soybean were found to have higher amino acid levels to support protein synthesis and essential metabolic processes for growth (Dabbou et al., 2021; Kanojia et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2019). Conversely, in Arabidopsis, oats, and tobacco, high amino acid levels in senescent leaves were linked to protein degradation during the onset of senescence (Soudry et al., 2005; Li et al., 2017). Thus, our findings align with the established dual role of amino acids in promoting both active growth and senescence.

This regulatory shift in ANF-treated plants is further underscored by the differential expression of senescence regulatory genes (Table 1). In US samples, the upregulation of WRKY transcription factors (WRKY52, WRKY53) and NAC factors (NAP1, NAP2)—along with ethylene biosynthesis genes (ACS2, ACO1)—were associated with accelerated senescence (Ay et al., 2009; Miao et al., 2004; Zentgraf et al., 2010; Ma et al., 2018; Qiu et al., 2015; Agarwal et al., 2012; Houben and Van de Poel, 2019; Kanojia et al., 2023). Additionally, the expression of SAG101 and MAPKKK53 in US leaves further suggests the active role of these pathways in promoting senescence under drought stress (Miryeganeh, 2022; Wu et al., 2014). In contrast, PU samples showed a distinct expression pattern, with the upregulation of WRKY3, WRKY70, and PP2C, all of which negatively regulate senescence (Durian et al., 2020; Hichri et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2023; Ülker et al., 2007). These findings coincided with impaired photosynthesis activity in US samples, as evidenced by the marked downregulation of photosynthesis-related GO terms only in US leaves, but not in PS leaves (Fig. 4). In several studies, biostimulants have shown to reduce the expression of senescence-related genes, such as moringa leaf extract delayed leaf senescence by modifying the source-sink relationship (Rehman et al., 2017, 2021; Yuniati et al., 2022). Similarly, an alkaline seaweed extract reduced the expression of senescence-related genes (*SAG 13* and *SAG*

21) in Arabidopsis, thereby providing protection from green peach aphids (Weeraddana et al., 2021). In conclusion, our study demonstrates that ANF enhances drought tolerance in tomato by modulating key physiological and molecular pathways, including the accumulation of amino acids to promote growth and suppress cellular senescence.

5. Conclusion

This study focused on plant priming to enhance stress tolerance and productivity, exploring the potential of ANF as a priming agent in drought-stressed tomato plants during the fruiting stage. The results provided crucial insights into the protective role of ANF and its potential to enhance drought stress tolerance under water-limited conditions.

Abiotic stress often reduces photosynthesis activity, overproduces ROS, and activates senescence, leading to poor crop yields. Our physiological, transcriptomic, and metabolomic data showed that ANF mitigates these drought-induced deteriorating changes in tomato plants. The model in Fig. 8 visually illustrates these findings, where ANF-primed tomato plants exposed to drought stress exhibited tolerance with elevated osmoprotectants, flavonoids, antioxidants, and sterols and maintained photosynthesis. Importantly, the onset of senescence was delayed during the vegetative phase in the primed plants at molecular level. The combined effects resulted in enhanced growth, larger fruit, and higher yields, while unprimed plants showed reduced fruit set, size, and yield accompanied by the onset of senescence, impaired photosynthesis, and decreased antioxidant and osmoprotectant levels, making them susceptible to drought stress.

In conclusion, as evidenced by our findings, the studied ANF acts as a protective shield, enhancing drought tolerance and promoting growth and fruit yield in tomatoes, making it a promising biostimulant. These findings provide valuable insights into the molecular mechanisms by which biostimulants mitigate stress in crops. Building on these findings, future studies should explore the role of the identified key genes involved in ANF-mediated stress responses in other crop species. Specifically, creating transgenic lines by overexpressing or silencing these key genes will allow researchers to test whether these modified crops

Fig. 8. Comparative model of drought response in ANF-primed vs. unprimed tomato plants. Drought tolerance in ANF-primed (left) and drought susceptibility in unprimed (right) tomato plants. Upward arrows represent increased levels, downward arrows signify reduced levels, and double-headed arrows denote the maintained levels. The figure was created using BioRender.com.

exhibit enhanced tolerance to multiple abiotic stresses. Additionally, it would be worthwhile to investigate the effects of ANF under different environmental conditions and across diverse crop varieties to assess its broader applicability in enhancing global agricultural resilience. Such studies could significantly contribute to the development of crops with built-in stress tolerance, ultimately reducing yield losses in the face of climate change.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Aakansha Kanojia: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Rafe Lyall:** Methodology, Data curation. **Neerakkal Sujeeth:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Saleh Alseekh:** Investigation. **Félix J. Martínez-Rivas:** Investigation. **Alisdair R. Fernie:** Investigation. **Tsanko S. Gechev:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Veselin Petrov:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

N.S is an employee of BioAtlantis Ltd. All other authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.stress.2024.100692](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.stress.2024.100692).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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